

A STUDY OF WOMEN AND PANDEMIC
Ms. Rajnandini Manjhi
Assistant Professor,
K.B. College of Arts and Commerce for Women, Thane (East)
Abstract:

The pandemic has disproportionately affected women. But you may not have realized the scope of the hit. It's extraordinarily significant—a tremendous toll. Women's experiences at home, their health, their work and economic wellbeing have all been negatively affected. And the pandemic has impeded women in the present, but also has negatively affected their futures.

But beyond these negative effects, organizations can take steps to make a positive impact. Here's what you must know about the scale of the damage and the potential responses

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eijr/>

Introduction:

The COVID 19 pandemic and the lockdown have resulted in a major shift in all aspects of work and life, everywhere across the world. It has posed a threat to everyone, however, the measures to combat this pandemic has overlooked the position of gender within this pandemic. One will have to understand and acknowledge the fact that women have been the most disproportionately lot in this pandemic. Physical distancing and stay- at-home which have become the new normal have had larger implications on women in every sphere of their lives. Like the rest of the country, long standing patriarchal social norms and cultural expectations have put the burden of caring for children, the elderly, and the household on the women from Assam as well. Women are spreading themselves thin as they bear the heightened burden of household responsibilities along with child care and elderly care. The pandemic has brought forth the correlation between the socially constructed moral obligation of care and the well being of the society. During the pandemic, women's health worsened across several areas, from nutrition to stress to reproductive services, according to public health officials and published reports. Often called a "hidden pandemic," violence against women, worryingly, also increased.

Healthcare access for women and girls has been disrupted, confinement measures increased gender-based violence, and girls disadvantaged and marginalised. Worryingly, it seems we are not learning from the past, as women and girls have encountered similar issues experienced during previous Health Crises.

Objectives:

The overall objective of this study is to analyze the Impact of COVID-19 on Women. In particular, this study will examine:

- * Crisis Women's have suffer during COVID-19
- * women's immolation due to pandemic.

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal

Volume-X, Issues-VI

Nov - Dec, 2021

Methodology:

Data and information presented in the study are collected from various reports, magazines and articles published by national and international agencies on impact of COVID-19 pandemic. Secondary methodology is been used.

Purpose of the Study:

This research will inform effective and appropriate outbreak response interventions, policies, and messages in every countries. Our research questions are: - What are the levels of COVID-19 awareness on womens and knowledge, risk on health perceptions? - What factors are associated with correct knowledge and preventive measures on women due to COVID-19?

Observation and Recommendation:

Every crisis impacts women and girls differently than men, because of existing gender norms and inequalities. To build back better and equal from the COVID-19 crisis, policy, investment and action must be shaped by women and girls and deliberately target them. UN Women is working with the government and grassroots organizations on the ground to provide food, personal protective equipment for women, and cash assistance.

Women's and girls at more risk of contracting COVID-19 than men:

Over 30 million people have been infected by the coronavirus in India. COVID-19 can infect people of all gender and ages. However, some women and girls may be at higher risk because they are poorer and lack information and resources, or because they are at the front line as caregivers and workers in the health and service sectors. In India, women make up a significant proportion of all healthcare workers and more than 80 per cent of nurses and midwives. Yet, when it comes to decision-making roles in the health sector, they are largely absent, and they get paid much less than their male counterparts. Only 13 per cent of the members of the national COVID-19 task force are women.

Since women in India spend more hours caring for children, the elderly and sick family members, and masks and other personal protective equipment are often designed and sized for men, women may be at risk of more exposure to the virus. Right now, there is also a concern that less women are getting vaccinated than men in India – 17 per cent more men than women have been partially or fully vaccinated, and according to national data, there are only two states where more women are taking the vaccine. Because of the fact that women have less access to internet or smart phones, they may not be able to register for vaccination. Due to the prevailing patriarchal norms, women may find it difficult to go to the vaccination centres alone, and there may be preference for male family members to get vaccinated first. There are also myths that vaccines compromise women's fertility. Unvaccinated women are at a high risk of contracting the disease, especially in the wake of the new variants

The second wave of COVID-19 in India brought unprecedented losses. The poorest and the most marginalized, including women and girls, face more risks without the means to absorb the economic shocks and mitigate the health crisis. They are caring for their families, sustaining livelihoods and leading efforts to fight the pandemic, amidst the threat of a third wave.

UN Women and health see it impacts women and girls in India

***COVID-19 impact on women's employment in India:**

Wage inequality and the burden of unpaid care has pushed more women out of employment and into poverty. Women's earned income in India was just one-fifth that of men's even before the pandemic. Globally, and in India, more women

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal

Volume-X, Issues-VI

Nov - Dec, 2021

have lost jobs during COVID-19. A recent report by the Center for Sustainable Employment at Azim Premji University in India shows that during the first lockdown in 2020, only 7 per cent of men lost their jobs, compared to 47 per cent of women who lost their jobs and did not return to work by the end of the year. In the informal sector, women fared even worse. This year, between March and April 2021, rural Indian women in informal jobs accounted for 80 per cent of job losses. Indian women also spend more time doing unpaid care work at home than men. On an average, they spend 9.8 times more time than men on unpaid domestic chores and 4.5 hours a day caring for children, elders and the sick. During the pandemic, their share of unpaid care work grew by nearly 30 percent.

The socio-economic toll on women and girls have long-term consequences, unless policies and actions deliberately target and invest in women. There is a risk that the exodus of women from the workforce could become permanent, reversing not only gender equality gains, but GDP gains. UN Women data [1] also shows that more girls than boys were left out of school during the pandemic and 65 per cent of parents surveyed were reluctant to continue the education of girls and resorting to child marriages to save costs. This can create an entire generation of young women without education and employment

Increased violence against women in India during COVID-19:

As the COVID-19 lockdowns trapped women at home with their abusers, domestic violence rates spiked throughout the world. In India, reports of domestic violence, child marriage, cyber violence and trafficking of women and girls increased within the first few months of the pandemic. According to the National Commission of Women data, India recorded a 2.5 times increase in domestic violence between February and May 2020. Some women's organizations reported that in the first four phases of the lockdown, they received more reports of domestic violence than they had in the last ten years for a similar period of time. Others indicated that many women were unable to report the violence, as they had less privacy and means to access help.

The Indian Government classified domestic violence shelter and support services as "essential" – an important step in COVID-19 response. During the first and second waves of the pandemic, 700 One-Stop-Crisis centres remained open in India, supporting over 300,000 women who suffered abuse and needed shelter, legal aid and medical attention. The current draft of the anti-trafficking bill that will be tabled soon in the Parliament is another welcome step, as it is set to increase penalties for perpetrators and make reporting of such crimes mandatory.

Through our communications campaigns, we are making sure that women get verified information about disease prevention and vaccination, and creating public awareness about gender-based violence. Through our programmes, we are making education and vocational training available for women through digital and distance learning, and helping them find pathways to employment and small businesses. We are working with our national partners to provide shelter, financial and legal assistance and medical help to survivors of gender-based violence in COVID-safe spaces. UN Women is advocating with the government and private sector allies to invest in the formal and informal care economies to create sustainable jobs and boost women's empowerment and income.

Conclusion:

COVID-19 has impacted vastly on Women's lives In Sum The pandemic has been tough, and especially for women. But the opportunity going forward is for us to influence systems and structures to provide more advantages and equity for women—and for people to support each other in the process of empowering and enabling women to improve their conditions and create fulfillment.

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal

Volume-X, Issues-VI

Nov - Dec, 2021

The social and economic impacts of COVID-19 fall harder on women than on men. Governments need to gather data and target policy to keep all citizens equally safe, sheltered and secure. The COVID-19 pandemic has devastated lives around the world, 4.6 million deaths and counting. The pandemic has exposed sharp economic and social inequalities and has widened the already existing gap with the most vulnerable in society, including unequal impacts affecting women and girls by virtue of their gender. The World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap report 2021 estimates there has been a step back of 39 years due to the pandemic.

References:

[https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/stories/2021/7/faq-women-and-covid-19-in-](https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/stories/2021/7/faq-women-and-covid-19-in-india#:~:text=As%20the%20COVID%2D19%20lockdowns,few%20months%20of%20the%20pandemic.)

[india#:~:text=As%20the%20COVID%2D19%20lockdowns,few%20months%20of%20the%20pandemic.](https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/stories/2021/7/faq-women-and-covid-19-in-india#:~:text=As%20the%20COVID%2D19%20lockdowns,few%20months%20of%20the%20pandemic.)

<https://www.concern.net/news/impact-of-covid-19-on-women-and-girls>

<https://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/a-greater-impact-on-women/article31465962.ece>